

D2.2

Report on the new methodology that
digital humanities make possible

Document Identifier

→D2.2 Report on the new
methodology that digital humanities
make possible

Date Due

→M28

Submission Date

→30th august 2021

Work Package 2

→ Languages and Translations

Lead Beneficiary

→KU Leuven

This project has received
the European union's
Horizon 2020 research and
innovation programme under
the Marie Skłodowska-Curie
grant agreement N°813547.

ITN-MIDA 813547

Trends and developments in online ethnography

By Eleonora Landucci (ESR 4)

Among the methods that contribute to make anthropology a multidisciplinary field of research, online ethnography is receiving increasing attention due to the unique condition that many ethnographers are now encountering. In fact, while the use of online research methods applied to ethnography has been explored since the 1990s, after 2020 the debate is growing exponentially. The Coronavirus pandemic has further undermined the idea of an in-depth, long-lasting and far-flung research field that was already questioned by many anthropologists far before the spread of COVID-19 (Faubion and Marcus, 2009; Amit, 2000; Gupta and Ferguson, 1997). In return, the interest in qualitative research methods that involve digital technologies or actually focused on ethnographing the digital sphere has drastically grown.

The pandemic may have reinforced this interest, however, since the 1990s there is an increasing attention from ethnographers to the use digital technologies (Goulden et al.,

2017). In this sense, the contacts between anthropology and Digital Humanities are now numerous: Digital Humanities means not only the use of digital tools and methods in humanities, but also the consideration of the «digital» as a research object. Online ethnography is situated precisely in these two aspects (Terras et al., 2013). But what exactly is “online ethnography”? And what are the major trends occurring within this methodology? The following report won’t provide an exhaustive answer to these questions but it will focus on some authors who have reflected on the epistemological, methodological and ethical challenges regarding online ethnography.

Online-, virtual-, cyber-, digital-, net- are all prefixes that accompany the term ethnography and which can indicate whether the use of ethnographic methods to investigate online contexts, a set of digital research methods applied to ethnographic inquiries and/or the observation of the Internet as “anthropological object”. Since when the Internet

Trends and developments in online ethnography

By Eleonora Landucci (ESR 4)

and the ITC began to be increasingly present in people's daily lives, social scientists have started to approach this research object with the epistemological implications that have resulted, namely by reflecting on polarised conceptualisations such as: whether to classify social interactions on the Internet as "real life" or "virtual life" (Turkle, 1995), or whether to consider the Internet as a "space" or as a "cultural product" (Benedikt, 1991; Woolgar, 1996). Christine Hine in her 2000's book "Virtual Ethnography" started to critically reflect on several crucial categories that are now often mobilised in the studies of the Internet in social sciences, especially those of "time", "communication", "identity" and "representation of the self/other". On a methodological level, the Internet as a research object has been presented and still presents many difficulties, being an ambiguous umbrella term which contains many meanings and undergoes many changes. Annette Markham (2017) observed how the liquidity of the Internet poses

several methodological issues to ethnography when it comes to circumscribing the "field", observing the "social actors" or gathering "data". She argues that ethnographers want to undertake an analysis of the Internet they need require new ontological bases and therefore develop adjusted methods of inquiry. This concern has been taken up by numerous scholars, especially those who have observed forms of interpersonal communication in the digital sphere (Markham, 2017; Bonilla and Rosa, 2015; Beneito-Montagut, 2011). This is because in ethnography, although unanimity is not always reached between the different traditions, we consider the researcher's experience as the starting point at the basis of anthropological knowledge.

The perspective adopted by these authors is that offline and online interactions have blurred and vague boundaries when it comes to forms of everyday interpersonal communication (Ibid.). As Roser Beneito-Montagut (2011) argued, this approach encounters the

ethnographers need to adapt their methodological tools to study the impact of the digital in the social. Indeed, when it comes to understand the impact of Internet phenomena into forms of verbal and non-verbal communication this perspective takes into account the individual use of online communication at its micro-level rather than its macro (Ibid.) and without focusing on a particular technology, but considering the individuals' experience of the internet. Beneito-Montagut refers to this methodological position as an 'expanded ethnography', "as it tries to capture individuals' use of online communication in a holistic manner" (Ibid.).

The ethnographic study of the digital sphere has also encountered several interesting debates around the ethical implication of doing research in an online environment. For instance, Katreen Tiidemberg (2018), who worked on trust and vulnerability on the Internet, suggested to look at a situational and feminist approach, allowing the researcher to build empathy,

understood an insight into the thoughts and feelings of others. By looking at the enjeux behind the ways in which selves and self-presentation are shaped in an online environment, she looked the ways in which different research ethics shaped her research. Finally, she advocated for an ethics of Care – understood as a relationship of caring and being cared for – might allow to approach the ethnographic relationship from a position of mutuality, kindness and respect (Ibid.) For Tiidemberg, what remains crucial, is to build a relationship based on case-by-case decision making and avoiding decontextualized and standardised ethical practices.

To conclude, the authors and debates regarding the developments and approaches of contemporary online ethnography are only part of an ever-changing field of research and it was not possible to go into detail on the ways in which the methods of the Digital Humanities meet those of the ethnography (i.e. introduction of programming

Trends and developments in online ethnography

By Eleonora Landucci (ESR 4)

languages or data visualization as tools for collecting, analysing and presenting ethnographic data). Finally, as a conclusive remark, it is important to notice that the pandemic has had and still has a major impact on the ways in which individuals access the Internet and interact in the digital sphere. Therefore, the purpose of online ethnography is to reflect on the main challenges and changes posed by the Coronavirus pandemic both to fieldworks and methods of ethnographic research online.

Digital Historical Research: An open science inspired workflow

By Elmozfar Kotoz Abdelhafiz (ESR 5)

The following is a sketch of a methodology for the digital practice of historical research that is guided first and foremost by the concept of open-science, not only in terms of the dissemination of results, but primarily in terms of exploiting the potential created by the free availability of vast amounts of digital information, navigating its already existing yet disparate infrastructure of connected research data.

The exponential growth of the field of Digital humanities in the previous years manifested in the development of a wide variety of tools aimed at handling an endless variety of sources and data. The very diverse and interdisciplinary nature of the label Digital Humanities (DH) often results in rather undefined debates; to which every participant brings their own tacit conception and definition about a field that is yet in the process of being defined. Accordingly, I firmly believe that any case specific invocation of DH needs to be further qualified in terms of the specific needs of the research case at hand, and the

unique characteristics of the discipline to which it is most aligned.

In the particular context of a historical inquiry into the emergence of modern transnational networks of scholarship; a plethora of tools are available to researchers at almost every stage and process of the research. The aim of the present paper is to offer a coherent workflow informed by the methodological logic of the research. At the heart of this logic is the fundamental process of the biographical profiling of historical actors. To serve as the fundamental building block of a machine assisted research, the biographical profiles of the studied actors depend on the careful modeling of the biographical information and sources in a relational design. The central conceptual challenge here is the balancing between the machine-readability of the biographical information/ sources and the preservation of their granularity and cognitive relationality.

Digital Historical Research: An open science inspired workflow

By Elmozfar Kotoz Abdelhafiz (ESR 5)

In more practical terms, the first challenge with which digital tools can be of enormous help is the initial processes of locating and accessing the primary sources of biographical research in digital spaces as the World Wide Web (WWW), or with the help of digital records/collection guides. This is significant in a digital landscape characterized with hastened and decentralized digitization that results in the production of fragmented and isolated collections of data/sources evading the grasp of researchers simply due to unconventional transliteration or naming and metadata schemes, which is the second major practical challenge. To that end, the aforementioned modeling process should always be relationally oriented and conscious of the existent landscape of connected and collaborative data points in the discipline. The final practical challenge in this regard is that of labor intensity. After locating a source and modeling the container, profile, which it is supposed it to fill, come the time consuming stages of data extraction and feeding. This very

diverse stage is often conflated with the term digitization in a problematic manner. For example, while the scanning of archived correspondence might be technically an act of digitization, these scans are valueless to the researchers until they are transcribed, coded, and organized in profiles in a meaningful way. Traditionally; these processes are very time and resource consuming, often beyond the means of most researchers.

I recognize eight central processes that compose the workflow of a digitally assisted historical research. And while there is no one-size-fits-all digital tool that works on all these processes, the current state of the art in DH offers the components for an integrated approach towards tackling the aforementioned challenges.

The first process is source-locating, in the context of my research this practically means the identification of members of the Arab-European orientalist networks and their surviving

Nachlässe. In the majority of cases, either these collections or records of them are available at the level of national libraries and recordkeepers. The metadata of such records are made available online by most major recordkeepers around the world, mostly in a machine readable format (i.e. RDF). Complemented with decentralized data-graphs such as Wikidata, these records are a formidable resource for source locating. Using a semantic query language for databases (SPARQL in my case), the locations and relations of multiple records around the world can be imported to a personal research database using a short script.

Once located, the second process is access to sources. This process is highly context-dependent, as some sources are available online and others only accessible on site, some are free and others require timely and costly reproductions. Therefore, approaches ranging from traveling to web-scraping can be utilized, with the final common goal of this stage being to have

the sources in question available to the researcher in one digital format or another.

Thirdly, there is the processing of the found sources into a digitally analysable corpus, this includes sub-processes such as digital scanning, restoration and formatting. This stage is also very context-dependent as the choice of applied processes must serve the overarching goals and methodology of the research in question. In my doctoral research, optical and graphical processing are of fundamental importance. In dealing with large quantities of scanned materials, a dependable toolset for OCR (transcribing images into digital text) and digital photo restoration is a must. This enables meaningful structuring on the database level, and the subsequent relational and computational analysis. Particularly in this stage, previous EU investments in artificial intelligence (AI) research is paying off spectacularly, with the Transkribus toolset developed by H2020 project READ being central to my research.

Digital Historical Research: An open science inspired workflow

By Elmozfar Kotoz Abdelhafiz (ESR 5)

The fourth process is organization, which is the fundamentally significant meaningful ordering of the information contained in collected sources. An excellent tool for preliminary data structuring and cleaning is OpenRefine, an extremely powerful open-source tool for data refining, clean up, and formatting. Above all however, my research is an exercise of relational data analysis and production, aiming to connect already existing and invested-in yet disparate knowledge on my research topic, and contributing new knowledge to the resulting network. To that end, the software suite Nodegoat is the most central tool to this research. An integrated data-modeling and dataset management software that specializes in object-oriented relational databases, Nodegoat enables the organization of historical sources while maintaining their relations to studied historical actors over a chronological continuum. Accordingly, the organization of research data in Nodegoat is truly the first stage

of relational analysis. In addition, it is a web-based, text-based and open-source toolset, offsetting any future concerns with legacy-software and format-rot. Fifth and most importantly is the process of analysis. Contrary to dominant orientation of computational analysis of large corpora of information in DH, I believe that in a context of a historical and biographical research the best utilization of DH tools is that of aids to a conventional approach of close reading of sources. To that end, relational analysis based on work already done in the organization process can be of tremendous analytical value. Tools such as Nodegoat and Gephi can be of great help at this stage, but close reading should remain as the main approach. Processes six and seven, dissemination and data-linking respectively, are very closely related and stem from a general paradigm shift driven by DH towards opening and interoperating research data. These two processes are operationally continuous with the first process of source-

locating forming a self-feeding loop, contributing to the very same sources the research emerged from. An accessible and well-structured dataset connected to authoritative linked-data platforms through the use of persistent identifiers (OCLC's VIAF authority identifiers and Wikidata) can be an invaluable source for the scientific community at large. The continuity between these two processes and the first process of source locating is a perfect manifestation of the open-science principle of self-perpetuating open data.

Digital Methods in Analyzing TV Series

By Mustafa Oğuzhan Çolak (ESR 6)

The usage of computational sciences methods on audio-visual data is still in the fledgling stage of development. Although only a few are familiar with the topic today, ongoing discussion on the digital tools for the field shows us researchers will employ these methods more frequently in the future. This report focuses on the new methodology that digital humanities make possible for the research on the TV series.

A movie is a collection of moving pictures and approximately including more than a hundred thousand images. When it comes to TV series, it would be billions of images in a single product. Each scene has its stylistic feature with the setting and light. Analyzing audio-visual data such as movies or TV series is mainly based on examining data by manual work. Dealing with this much audio-visual data brings a real challenge for researchers to investigate the whole collection from a comprehensive, scientific, and objective perspective. Computational methods would

help us to deal with this obstacle by providing powerful tools. In my research, I am examining a specific TV series named Payitaht: Abdülhamid, consisting of 54 episodes with almost 8500 minutes duration. The drama's plot develops as the Sultan discovers his enemies' despicable dispositions to destroy his Empire. After employing conventional film analysis methods, I noticed an anti-semitic and anti-catholic narrative by promoting three central symbols representing the archenemies: the Star of David for the Jewish community, Keys of Heaven for the Catholics, and the Sigil of Baphomet for the Freemasons.

I have been developing a Computer Vision algorithm to identify particular symbols in the series with my colleagues Dr. Peter Verhaar and Ben Companjen from the Center for Digital Humanities of Leiden University. Computer Vision algorithm allows us to recognize these particular objects, such as the star of David, the pentagram, and the keys of heaven, which

have a reasonably consistent visual appearance. The algorithm also makes it possible to calculate the screen time allotted to each of these symbols and also facilitates focusing on significant objects that are vital for analyzing the series. In other words, we can employ both a quantitative and large-scale investigation and qualitative film analysis together to reach a more detailed examination of the scenes.

Each TV series has some stylistic elements like setting, light, and camera angle. The producer manipulates the image with lights and camera angles to influence the audience's interpretation and reaction. So, scholars should focus on these stylistic elements in analyzing TV series, and working on these stylistic elements demands much effort. Employing a Computer Vision algorithm is a more time and energy-efficient way to examine the stylistic feature of a TV series. Moreover, scholars can implement algorithms with slight changes on different audio-visual data.

The usage of computational methods also provides scholars to do text analysis and audience-reception research on TV series. Researchers may prefer to work on scripts as one of the main parts of the series, and text mining methods facilitate analyzing hundreds of pages of text for them. Text mining helps researchers in identifying meaningful patterns by implementing advanced analytical techniques on the scenario. Scholars also can apply the audience-reception research by scraping comments on social media like the audience reactions on official Instagram and YouTube channels of the series. Computational tools help scholars use quantified data as additional evidence for hypotheses and interpret large amounts of data. Specifically, sentiment analysis is an effective vehicle to analyze audience comments by categorizing them as positive, negative, or neutral. In conclusion, digital methods enable scholars to perform a comprehensive and systematic analysis and interpretation of selected scenes with less

Digital Methods in Analyzing TV Series

By Mustafa Oğuzhan Çolak (ESR 6)

effort. Even the computational techniques are pretty new in TV series analysis, stimulating a discussion on the future of digital tools for the field would be a great starting point. The brain-storm on the possibilities created by Computer Vision and other digital methods would allow researchers to initiate further discussions on digital data analysis and their relation to more traditional methodologies. In my opinion, digital tools and computational methods are not a replacement of qualitative interpretation of research data or reception analysis, but it mainly provides an additional tool to verify qualitative hypotheses. Therefore, computational methods could be supported or compared with the conventional way of film and text analysis.

Selected bibliography

Amit, V. (2000). Constructing the field: Ethnographic fieldwork in the contemporary world. Routledge.

Benedikt, M. (1991). *Cyberspace: First steps*. MIT Press.

Beneito-Montagut, R. (2011). Ethnography goes online: Towards a user-centred methodology to research interpersonal communication on the internet: *Qualitative Research*, 11, 716–735. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794111413368>

Boellstorff, T., Nardi, B. A., Pearce, C., Taylor, T. L., & Marcus, G. E. (2012). *Ethnography and virtual worlds: A handbook of method*. Princeton University Press.

Bonilla, Y., & Rosa, J. (2015). #Ferguson: Digital protest, hashtag ethnography, and the racial politics of social media in the United States: *#Ferguson. American Ethnologist*, 42, 4–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/amet.12112>

Broek, E. van den, Sergeeva, A. V., & Huysman, M. (2021). When the Machine Meets the Expert: An Ethnography of Developing AI for Hiring. *MIS Quarterly*.

Chen, S. (2018). Big Data in

Computational Social Science and Humanities (Computational Social Sciences) (1st ed. 2018 ed.). Springer.

Cioffi-Revilla, C. (2017). *Introduction to Computational Social Science: Principles and Applications (Texts in Computer Science)* (2nd ed.). Springer.

Coleman, E. G. (2010). Ethnographic Approaches to Digital Media. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 39, 487–505.

Couldry, N. (2015). The myth of 'us': Digital networks, political change and the production of collectivity. *Information, Communication & Society*, 18, 608–626. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2014.979216>

Dalal, S. (2019). Reviewing the Role of Netnographic Research in Bridging the Gap between Youngsters and Adults. *Global Journal of Archaeology & Anthropology*, 7, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.19080/GJAA.2019.07.555723>

Selected bibliography

Drucker, J. (2021). The Digital Humanities Coursebook: Principles and Methods for Digital Scholarship. Routledge.

Evans, S. (2013). Virtual Selves, Research Perspectives: Exploring the Role and Implications for Taking the Insider Perspective in Virtual Worlds Research. In P. Jerry, N. Tavares-Jones, & S. Gregory (Eds.), *Riding the Hype Cycle* (pp. 199–218). Inter-Disciplinary Press. https://doi.org/10.1163/9781848882348_019

Faubion, J. D., & Marcus, G. E. (2009). Fieldwork is not what it used to be: Learning anthropology's method in a time of transition. Cornell University Press.

Goulden, M., Greiffenhagen, C., Crowcroft, J., McAuley, D., Mortier, R., Radenkovic, M., & Sathiaselan, A. (2017). Wild interdisciplinarity: Ethnography and computer science. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 20(2), 137–150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2016.1152022>

Gupta, A., & Ferguson, J. (1997). Anthropological locations: Boundaries and grounds of a field science. University of California Press.

Hassaballah, M., & Awad, A. I. (2020). Deep Learning in Computer Vision: Principles and Applications (Digital Imaging and Computer Vision) (1st ed.). CRC Press.

Hine, C. (2000). Virtual Ethnography. SAGE.

Kozinets, R. V. (2002). The Field behind the Screen: Using Netnography for Marketing Research in Online Communities. *Journal of Marketing Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.39.1.61.18935>

Mariani, P., & Zenga, M. (2020). Data Science and Social Research II: Methods, Technologies and Applications (Studies in Classification, Data Analysis, and Knowledge Organization Book 2) (1st ed. 2021 ed.). Springer.

Pang, B., & Lee, L. (2008). Opinion Mining and Sentiment Analysis.

Foundations and Trends® in Information Retrieval, 2(1–2), 1–135. <https://doi.org/10.1561/15000000011>

Ploug, T. (2009). Ethics in Cyberspace: How Cyberspace May Influence Interpersonal Interaction. Springer Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-2370-4>

Smits, T., & Wevers, M. (2021). The agency of computer vision models as optical instruments. *Visual Communication*, 147035722199209. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1470357221992097>

Terras, M. M., Nyhan, J., & Vanhoutte, E. (2013). Defining digital humanities: A reader.

Tiidenberg, K. (2018). Research Ethics, Vulnerability, and Trust on the Internet. In J. Hunsinger, L. Klastrup, & M. M. Allen (Eds.), *Second International Handbook of Internet Research* (pp. 1–15). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-024-1202-4_55-1

Turkle, S. (1995). Life on the screen: Identity in the age of the Internet. Simon & Schuster.

Woolgar, S., & Dutton, W. H. (1996). Technologies as cultural artefacts. In *Information and Communication Technologies: Visions and Realities*. Oxford University Press.